

FIRST TRIMESTER BODY MASS INDEX IN SMALL FOR GESTATIONAL AGE NEONATES

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Introduction: Small for gestational age (SGA) is heterogeneous condition which includes constitutionally small fetuses and intrauterine growth restriction. It is believed that early placental development (vasculogenesis and angiogenesis) and maternal pre pregnancy characteristics (high overweight, obesity, cigarette smoking, hypertension, diabetes) have impact on pregnancy outcome, including delivering small for gestational age neonates. Material and methods: This study was conducted as prospective study between January 2013 and September 2014 at Department of Gynecology and Obstetrics, Clinical centre of Vojvodina, Novi Sad. Study include 46 pregnancies between 11.-14 week of gestation, 29 in control group and 17 in study group. Study group was pregnancies with small for gestational age neonates (birth weight was below 10th for gestational age) and control group with birth weight in reference age for gestational age. BMI was calculated in the first trimester to all participants. Results: Pregnancies in study group had statistically higher mean values of BMI in the first trimester than control group ($28,54 \pm 3,5$, $25,77 \pm 2,42$, $p < 0,001$ respectively). Values of hsCRP in the first trimester was also significantly higher in study group ($4,54 \pm 3,21$, $2,43 \pm 1,74$, $p < 0,001$ respectively). There were no differences between the groups according to the values of CBC, urea, creatinin, uric acid, electrolytes and glucose. Conclusion: The results of this study could indicate that first trimester body mass index have impact on pregnancy outcome – SGA. It could be that pre pregnancy burden of the mother with endothelial activation already before pregnancy have impact on early placental development, causing angiogenic imbalance and worsening of maternal endothelial dysfunction.